

BENCH-MARKING OF 3D PREFORMING STRATEGIES

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SUMMARY

This paper evaluates various 3D preforming strategies for tensile stiffness, strength and ILSS. Normalised to 50% fibre volume fraction, 3D woven, stitched and tufted laminates show similar trend; differences can be accounted for by the tow crimp and distortion during stitching. Robotic fibre placed, tufted samples exhibit highest tensile properties and good ILSS values.

Keywords: through-thickness, stitching, 3D weaving, Robotic fibre placement, tufting

INTRODUCTION

3D weaving has caught the imagination of the aerospace industry in recent years as a means of producing dry textile preforms with reduced part-count and improved damage tolerance. Messier-Dowty's landing gear strut for Boeing 787, JSF inlet duct and Snecma motor's [1] aero-engine fan blade are some of the high profile applications for 3D woven preforms. This trend for 3D weaving will continue in the next few years as the industry is working towards out-of-autoclave technologies involving dry preforms and liquid moulding techniques.

Figure 1 shows examples of 3D weaves including orthogonal, angle interlocked, layer-to-layer interlocked structures. These fabrics are relatively easy to produce on electronic Jacquard looms. However, there are a number of limitations including,

- 3D weaving machines can produce a flat rectangular slab of material – it is possible, but not easy to change the width or thickness of the preform in order to achieve taper,
- 3D woven composites suffer from a reduction in in-plane modulus due to fibre waviness that occurs during repeated shedding.
- It is not easy to drape or mould 3D woven preforms as this may lead to significant tow distortions and local micro buckling.
- In 3D weaves, the fibre orientations are mainly in three orthogonal directions – it is not easy to introduce off-axis tows
- Relatively thick preforms require purpose-built take-up devices, as they can not wrap around take-up rollers.

There has been a general misunderstanding in the composites industry that 3D weaving is the answer to every preforming requirement. Industry expects to 'weave' complex shapes with single/double curvatures, arbitrary boundaries, multi-axial fibre orientations and with through-thickness reinforcement. Clearly, 3D weaving cannot achieve all these

requirements. We need to consider several preforming strategies rather than focusing on 3D weaving.

Figure 1: 3D weaves: a) orthogonal b) angle interlocked c) layer-to-layer interlocked

3D PREFORMING METHODS

In order to overcome the limitations of 3D weaving, we are looking at alternate 3D preforming strategies. In the present study, we consider three preforming techniques

- 3D weaving
- Stitching of 2D broadcloth
- Robotic fibre placement with tufting

3D Weaving

Conventional weaving machines equipped with an electronic Jacquard (figure. 2) are capable of producing a variety of 3D weaves (figure 1), ranging from orthogonal, angle interlocked to a variety of layer-to-layer interlocked weaves. However, these machines are suitable for relatively thin 3D fabrics [2]. Fibre damage and distortion may result in conventional weaving due to repeated sheddings. On the other hand, purpose built 3D weaving machines [3] can produce thick 3D weaves with significantly reduced fibre distortion. 3D weaving is generally good at producing fabrics of constant width and thickness. Some near-net shaping capabilities on weaving machines have been explored recently [4]. However, the fibre orientations in 3D woven preforms are restricted to 0° and 90° . Additionally, thicker 3D fabrics have limited drapeability and hence restricting their use to components with gentle curvatures.

Figure 2: Weaving machine

Multi-needle Stitching

Stitching has an additional preforming flexibility in a sense that a number of plies can be stacked in preferred orientations (eg. 0 , 90 , $+45$, -45) before stitching. Conventional single needle stitching is a relatively slow process. Recently, a multi-needle stitching

facility (figure 3a) has been developed at the University of Manchester. This machine can stitch through a thick stack of fabrics using a row of needles (with each needle having a yarn supplied from a creel). Once the loops are formed (figure 3a), a rapier inserts a locking thread across. One disadvantage with this system is potential fibre damage or distortion during needle insertion. Previous studies on stitching [5] showed that the extent of damage depends on process parameters. Again, this type of stitching is suitable for flat panels. Curved parts can be stitched using a Robotic stitching head at QinetiQ [6] –this will be included in the future test programme.

Figure3: a) Multi-needle stitching b) Robotic fibre placement with tufting

Robotic Fibre placement and Tufting

As an alternative to 3D weaving, robotic fibre placement process has been developed at Manchester University [7]. Using this process, fibres can be deposited into near-net shapes in 0° , 90° and $\pm\theta$ orientations using pins to locate the tow ends (figure 3b). Once the required number of layers is deposited, a tufting head attached to the robot creates through-thickness reinforcement. After tufting, the preform can be handled like a dry fabric and placed on a mould surface for resin infusion. Additional advantage of this system is that the fibres can be deposited on curved surfaces having arbitrary boundaries. Hence, this technique can lead to near-net preforming. Fibre deposition rates are much slower than weaving. However, if one takes into consideration the warping, drawing-in and loom setting times, robotic fibre placement is advantageous over weaving. Weaving is still preferred for mass production of broadcloth. In a previous study [8], tufting had shown to significantly improve the delamination resistance at a slight cost to the in-plane properties.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Preform Manufacture

This study focuses on three competing 3D preforming processes in terms of the influence of through-thickness reinforcement on composite laminate properties. Three biaxial 3D preforms with E glass have been produced for comparative study. An angle interlocked fabric was produced on a Dornier rapier loom equipped with Staubli Electronic Jacquard. Three plain woven fabric layers were stitched together using a 300 tex glass yarn. A multi-layer biaxial preform has been created using Robotic fibre

placement machine and tufted with a 300 tex glass yarn. The preform specifications are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: 3D Preform Specifications

Fabric Structure	Warp density ends/cm	Weft density ends/cm	Yarn count (Tex)			Stitch Spacing (mm)
			warp	weft	z-dir	
3D woven	14.1	10	900	600	-	-
Stitched	15.5	10.2	900	600	300	5 x 5
Tufted	12	12	600	600	300	5 x 5

Table 2: Crimp and Area density of 3D preforms

Fabric Structure	Crimp (%)		Areal Density (g/m ²)
	Warp	weft	
3D woven	3	0.15	1841
Stitched	1.1	0.77	2175
Tufted	0	0	1560

Composite Laminate Manufacture

Composite laminates have been produced by Vacuum infusion process using room temperature Epoxy system (Araldite LY5052 resin & Aradur 5052 CH hardener)

Table 3: Composite Laminate Properties

Fabric Structure	Fibre volume fraction (%) (V _f)	Fibre volume fraction in each direction (%)			Laminate Thickness (mm)
		Warp	Weft	Z direction	
3D woven	46.5	30.69	15.81	-	1.79
Stitched	43.5	27.40	13.48	2.39	2.0
Tufted	31.14	14.38	14.38	2.38	1.85

PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL TESTING

X Rays Tomography

To support the test results, X rays tomography machine has been used to investigate the internal structure of all composite samples. Tomography helps to visualize the internal structure of the specimen such as tow waviness, nesting, voids, resin rich areas etc. There is a good contrast between glass tow and the epoxy resin.

Figure 4 a) Tomography images of 3D woven (angle interlock) laminate

Figure 4a shows the through thickness interlacement of warp tows. It can be seen that weft crimp is relatively small and mainly results from nesting of warp tow.

Figure 4 b) Tomography images of stitched laminate

Tomography images of stitched plain woven laminate (Fig 4b) shows good degree of nesting in warp and weft direction. In the plane of stitches, running in the warp direction, resin rich pockets and voids can be seen. These stitches have distorted the weft tows with a potential negative impact on the mechanical properties in the weft direction. It may be possible to reduce the resin rich areas by adjusting the stitching parameters. This will be attempted in the next phase of investigations.

Figure 4 c) Tomography images of Robotic fibre placed and tufted laminate

It can be seen from the tufted laminate images (Fig 4c) that the tows are straight and stacked perfectly on top of each other without any nesting. This is due to the holding pins used in Robotic tow deposition. Additionally, there is no damage observed during tufting, and the tufting loops are positioned accurately between the tows. The negative impact of lack of nesting is the significant reduction in fibre volume fraction. This can be improved in future trials by reducing the tow spacing or using a wider spread tow.

Mechanical Testing

Tensile and short beam shear tests were conducted on all three laminates using an Instron test machine equipped with a 100kN cell load. The test speed was 2mm/min for tensile tests and 1mm/min for short beam test. Table 4 and figure 5 present the tensile test results. The tensile test data has been normalised to an idealised cross ply laminate with 50% fibre volume fraction, with equal fibres in each principal direction.

Table 4: Tensile Test Results

Fabric Structure	Tensile Modulus Actual (GPa)		Tensile Modulus normalised to 50% V_f (GPa)		Tensile Strength (MPa)		Tensile strength normalised to 50% V_f (MPa)	
	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft
Angle Interlock	15.36	9.18	12.80	15.31	326.14	234.14	265.67	370.3
Stitched	17.84	6.90	16.52	12.79	321.52	141.12	293.35	261.7
Tufted	13.61	12.88	23.66	22.40	271.09	314.69	471.29	547.0

Figure 5: Tensile Tests

Short beam tests were conducted on the three laminates in order to estimate the inter-laminar shear strength (Table 5). Figure 6 presents the short beam test results in terms of cross-head displacement versus load.

Table 5: Inter-laminar Shear strength of laminates

Fabric Structure	Inter-laminar shear strength (MPa)		
	Warp	Weft	Average
Angle Interlock	26.98	18.32	22.65
Stitched	19.70	15.49	17.60
Tufted	21.30	21.45	21.38

Figure 6: Short beam shear tests

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

Figure 7 compares tensile modulus for the three samples in the warp and weft direction. There is a significant difference between warp and weft directions. However, after normalisation, warp and weft data is much closer.

Figure 7: Tensile modulus before and after normalisation

In case of angle interlocked 3D woven laminate, tensile modulus in the warp direction is lower due to higher warp crimp. However, in the case of stitched samples, warp direction has higher modulus inspite of having a slightly higher crimp. This discrepancy can be explained with the help of figure 8. It can be seen that stitching yarn distorts the weft tow resulting in lower tensile modulus in weft direction. Tufted samples exhibit highest modulus due to the fact that Robotic tow placement results in nearly straight tow. Similar trend can be observed with respect to tensile strength (figure 9).

Fig8: weft distortion due to stitching

Figure 10 shows correlation with negative slope between tow crimp and tensile modulus/strength. This is entirely expected. The scatter is mainly due to the tow distortion of stitched samples in the weft direction. If the stitching tensions are properly adjusted, we may get improved correlation.

Figure 9: Tensile strength before and after normalisation

Figure 10: Correlation of tensile modulus and strength with crimp

Figure 11 presents inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) values for all the three samples. ILSS cannot be normalised with fibre volume fractions as this is an interface phenomena. ILSS is highest for the angle interlocked laminate. Brant et al[9] in their classic paper on 3D woven composites found that orthogonal weave has the highest ILSS value compared to orthogonal weaves; stitched and tufted preforms have geometry closer to orthogonal weaves. Stitched laminates have the lowest ILSS value may be due to the fibre distortion and damage in comparison to tufted samples.

Figure 11: ILSS values

CONCLUSION

Composite laminates were produced using 3D woven, stitched and tufted preforms. In-plane properties, after normalisation to 50% FVF, have a good correlation (with negative slope) with crimp. Fibre damage and distortion is higher in case of woven and stitched samples in comparison to Robotically stitched and tufted sample. ILSS values are highest for angle interlocked samples and slightly lower for tufted samples and lowest for stitched samples. Further work is required to improve our understanding of preform architecture on compression/compression after impact properties.

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